

FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF EPOXY COATING ON COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO WATERDROP IMPACT

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Summary

Modelling

- Finite Element modelling: Explicit Dynamics tool in ANSYS.
- Composite specimen: 10x10 mm rectangular cross-section.
- Raindrop: 3 mm diameter Sphere.
- Composite: Unidirectional S-Glass/epoxy, 2 mm thickness.
- Gel-coat: Epoxy resin, 0.6 mm thickness.
- Water drop impingement velocity: 140 m/s.

Rainfall Data

- Rainfall data of three years 2015, 2016 and 2017 is obtained for Mumbai, India
- Average time interval between two consecutive drops is 9.52 seconds
- Average rainfall duration is 750 hours/year
- Single impact damage is considered for fatigue life calculations

Fatigue life Prediction

- Rainflow cycle counting method
- The mean stress ratio correction
- Palmgren-Miner's Cumulative Damage accumulation rule

Direction	X	Y	Z	Material	Material model	Mesh	Reference Frame
Displacement of the base of the plate	Free	Free	0 (ramped)	S-Glass/UD	Orthotropic	Hexahedral	Lagrangian
Velocity of the droplet	0	0	-140 m/s	Epoxy resin	Isotropic	Hexahedral	Lagrangian
				Water	Shock EOS	Tetrahedral	Eulerian

Modelling

Along the cross-section	
Edge sizing type	Biased
Biased type	
Growth factor	1.05
No of divisions	100
Total edges	16
Along the thickness	
Edge sizing type	Uniform
Total edges	8
Number of divisions (coat)	12
Number of divisions (Composite)	40
Eulerian domain cell count	7x10 ⁵
Element size	0.06 mm

Body Interaction	Coat to drop	Frictionless
Body Interaction	Coat to composite	Bonded
Simulation time		10 μs
Time-step		0.01 μs
Time-step safety factor		0.2

Fatigue and Rainfall Data

Year	Station	Drops/hour (rain gauge)	Drops/hour (10x10 plate)	Drops/year (10x10 plate)	Time interval (s)	Duration of rainfall (hours)
2015	SCZ	24223	308	13112	11.68831169	606
2015	COL	26390	335	11851	10.74626866	611
2016	SCZ	27779	353	16779	10.19830028	955
2016	COL	27779	353	14302	10.19830028	851
2017	SCZ	50002	636	17255	5.660377358	772
2017	COL	32779	417	13625	8.633093525	695

Results and Conclusions

- This paper presents a model for the fatigue life prediction of epoxy coating against the raindrop impact.
- The rainfall data for the Mumbai, India permits considering a single impact damage for the study.
- This can be used as a fairly reasonable model for fatigue life prediction of different wind turbine coatings.
- The epoxy coating fails against 1040 raindrop impacts.
- The coating could offer a higher fatigue life in the low rainfall areas.
- Different boundary conditions on the specimen could vary the obtained results.
- The fatigue life variation with the coating thickness is to be studied to obtain the optimum coating thickness.

Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress vs time history

